

USE OF SEWING PRODUCTS IN HEALTHY DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada qad-qomatning noto'g'ri rivojlanishi natijasida kelib chiqadigan kasalliklarni oldini olish maqsadida foydalaniladigan tikuv mahsulotlari turlari va tavsiyalari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar. Qomat shakllanishi, umurtqa assimetrriyasi, qomatni tuzatuvchi bandaj.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ШВЕЙНЫХ ИЗДЕЛИЙ ДЛЯ ЗДОРОВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕТЕЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются виды и рекомендации по пошиву изделий, применяемых для профилактики заболеваний, вызванных аномальным ростом.

Ключевые слова. Формирование тела, асимметрия позвоночника, корригирующие повязки.

THE USE OF SEWING PRODUCTS FOR CHILDREN'S HEALTHY DEVELOPMENT

Annotation. This article analyzes the types and recommendations of sewing products used to prevent diseases caused by abnormal growth.

Keywords. Body formation, spinal asymmetry, body corrective bandage.

The formation of stature is important throughout life. A healthy lifestyle has important effects on the correct formation of height. The correct formation of stature plays a key role in the aesthetics of clothing and prevention of several diseases of old age. It is necessary to pay attention to the correct formation of stature from the birth of a child. Children under the age of 4-5 should not be led by adults for a long time, because the spine may be bent due to the fact that one side of the child rises up. When walking, he should keep his head upright, take moderate steps, not stoop, and

frequently change his body position and type of work during work class. In children and adolescents, various forms of scoliosis often distort the stature due to defects such as flat feet and joint disease. It is also necessary to pay attention to the child's sleep at night. The child should sleep in a flat place with a slightly firm blanket. Some children sleep like babies. Such a condition also affects height, children and teenagers should be taught from a young age to engage in physical exercises that help to form the correct height. For example: Gymnastics, swimming, volleyball, pull-ups, etc. Distortion of height not only affects the appearance of a person, but also negatively affects the development and function of internal organs (such as lungs, heart, liver, kidneys, stomach and intestines). When such people do physical work, engage in physical education and sports, they feel short of breath, their heart beats faster, and they get tired quickly [4]. The formation of stature continues until the age of 18. At the age of 7-11, the bones of the hands gradually harden. Distortion of stature is considered a disease in the early stages. It is mostly seen as a disease or enlargement of the spine in its natural state. It is represented by the appearance of the shoulder line in the position of asymmetry, in the chest in relation to the head. Such changes have a functional style. Insufficient attention by adults to the formation of the correct height in children - leads to a certain degree of disturbance in the development of the body. will bring. It is this condition that develops during the transition from one youth period to another. In their normal structure, the foot structure rests on the outer long support, which creates flexibility in walking. Children with stunted growth are not recommended to engage in certain types of sports, it is recommended to replace vigorous activity with physical minutes; special exercises related to the muscles of the back, abdominal muscles, and shoulders are recommended [5]. Various devices can be used for the correct development of stature. In particular, various types of bandages with a strap, which is a product of sewing products, give a good effect. When it is determined that such bandages are felt in the proper development of the body, it is considered necessary to use these devices based on the recommendation of doctors.

Figure 1. Types of healing bandages.

Samples of shape-correcting bandages of various forms are considered above. These devices are produced in different countries at different prices. The development of bandages with convenient construction and technology for mass use at a low cost will effectively benefit children's healthy development.

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